

BEHAVIOUR OF COPRECIPITATED NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ CATALYSTS FOR LOW-TEMPERATURE METHANE STEAM REFORMING

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Abstract

The suitability of the nickel aluminate phase as an effective precursor for producing highly active and stable Ni/alumina catalysts was investigated in the steam reforming of methane with a H₂O/CH₄ ratio of 3 in the 450-650 °C temperature range. Particularly, the effect of the preparation route, including dissolution followed by crystallization, coimpregnation and coprecipitation, for obtaining either bulk or alumina-supported samples was analyzed. A special attention was paid to examining the characteristics of the calcined catalytic precursors with a Ni content varying between 17-33 wt.%, namely textural properties, composition, nature and relative abundance of the existing nickel phases (NiAl₂O₄ and NiO) and reducibility. These properties were in turn correlated with the Ni crystallite size, dispersion and metallic surface area obtained after a severe high-temperature reduction step (850 °C). The best reforming performance (with a methane conversion of 78% and yield of hydrogen of 1.63 at 650 °C and 38000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹) was achieved by a reduced alumina-supported (17 wt.%Ni)NiAl₂O₄ catalyst prepared by coprecipitation although its behavior was influenced by a rapid, slight sintering. The coprecipitated bulk spinel, with a considerably higher Ni loading, showed a similar reforming behavior.

1. Introduction

In a world preoccupied by environmental threats, such as green house effect gas emissions and high energy costs, fuel cells are promising ‘chemical energy-to-electricity’ converters for both stationary and transportation applications. As a consequence, steam reforming of hydrocarbons has seen increasing interest due to the

necessity of efficient and cost-effective reforming technologies for hydrogen production. Steam reforming has the advantage of producing a higher H₂ concentration than partial oxidation since no H₂ is associated with the oxidant (O₂). In addition, partial oxidation is an exothermic reaction, and hot spots at the catalytic bed are a usual technical drawback, which leads to higher catalyst aging rates.

In practice, steam reforming of hydrocarbons, especially that of methane, is typically performed at high temperatures (700-900 °C) over Ni-based catalysts where the lower cost of nickel is an important advantage.^{1,2} This scenario (low-cost and long-proven performance of Ni-based catalysts) along with the need of reduction of energy input and material cost still warrants the effort to optimize these catalysts for steam reforming applications operating at low temperatures (<700 °C). Ideally, the catalyst must activate methane at low temperature, drive its conversion up to equilibrium values, operate at high volume hourly space velocity (VHSV, typically >10000 cm³ CH₄ min⁻¹ g⁻¹) and be resistant to deactivation.^{3,4} In order to avoid substantial coke formation, which is thermodynamically favored at low temperatures, a H₂O/CH₄ ratio varying between 2 and 4 is generally used.

Catalytic behavior as well as resistance to deactivation (coke formation and/or sintering and/or oxidation of metallic Ni active phase) is strongly influenced by metal-support (typically alumina) interactions which in turn have a notable effect on the size and the thermal stability of Ni particles.⁵⁻¹⁰ An adequate preparation route for obtaining small particles of the active metal dispersed on the support can be based on the use of suitable precursor materials where Ni is homogeneously distributed in an oxide structure such as MNiO₃ or NiM₂O₄. After a severe reduction step, which entails enhanced metal-support interactions, an active Ni/MO_x system can be then obtained.¹¹⁻¹⁶

Several authors have pointed out that NiAl_2O_4 spinel can be a promising precursor to develop suitable $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts for hydrocarbons reforming.¹⁷⁻²¹ Usually the NiAl_2O_4 catalytic phase is prepared by reacting either a Ni precursor salt with alumina or Ni and Al precursor salts. Occasionally this spinel is used as a support for Ni or other active metals such as rhodium.^{19,22} The reforming activity of these reduced NiAl_2O_4 catalysts is typically superior in comparison with other structurally similar phases such as CuAl_2O_4 ,¹⁷ NiFe_2O_4 ²³ or NiMn_2O_4 .²³ Usually a high-temperature reduction due to the stability of the crystalline NiAl_2O_4 phase is necessary to efficiently extract nickel from the structure and thus obtain metallic crystallites with an adequate reforming activity.²⁴⁻

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Our previous work showed that a better reforming behavior of NiAl_2O_4 catalysts could be achieved when the spinel precursor was deposited on an alumina carrier with respect to the bulk counterpart.^{27,28} These findings were observed for samples prepared by codissolution followed by crystallization (bulk NiAl_2O_4) and coimpregnation ($\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$). More recently, it has been established that coprecipitation is a more suitable route for optimizing the reforming efficiency of bulk nickel aluminate (33 wt.Ni%).²⁹ In this paper attention was focused on the study of low-temperature steam reforming behavior of $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts prepared by coprecipitation with a significantly lower Ni loading (17 and 24 wt.%). The objective was to increase the metallic surface area and dispersion of the resultant catalysts so as to obtain systems with a similar or even superior performance with respect to the pure spinel. In order to better assess the notable reforming behavior of these samples their performance has been compared with other previously examined spinel-derived $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts. This study has been carried out by combining characterization results of the calcined and reduced samples (including WDXRF, BET measurements, H_2 -TPR, XRD, UV-vis-NIR,

XPS and TEM), catalytic results at various reaction temperatures (450, 550 and 650 °C) during 12.5 h at each temperature. Also an attempt was made to compare the behavior of our samples with that of a wide variety of nickel catalysts found in the literature for low-temperature steam reforming of methane.

2. Experimental

2.1. Catalysts preparation. Two alumina supported samples with a Ni loading of 17 and 24 wt.% were prepared by coprecipitation (CP/A samples). The coprecipitation process was conducted by the drop-by-drop addition of a 0.6 M solution of NH_4OH (350-400 cm^3) under constant stirring into an aqueous solution (50 cm^3) of a mixture of nickel acetate and aluminum nitrate (1:2 Ni/Al molar ratio) and $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ alumina (133 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, 0.3-0.5 mm, SA 6173, Saint-Gobain). The amounts of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{-COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Aldrich) and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) were 7.3 g and 21.9 g, respectively, for the CP/A(17) sample and 18 g and 54.7 g, respectively, for the CP/A(24) sample. The temperature was kept at 25 °C. The initial pH was about 3 and it took two hours to reach a value equal to 8. Afterwards, the precipitates were aged for 30 minutes at this pH value before being filtered and washed with hot deionized water.

For comparative purposes two bulk NiAl_2O_4 (33 wt.%Ni) were obtained by dissolution and subsequent crystallization (D(33) sample) and coprecipitation with ammonium hydroxide (CP(33) sample). On the other hand, a $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ with a 24 wt.%Ni content was also synthesized by coimpregnation (CI/A(24) sample).²⁷⁻²⁹ All these catalytic precursors were dried at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 4 h at a heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} in order to provoke the formation of the NiAl_2O_4 phase. Pellets of the prepared catalysts (D(33) and CP(33) samples) were

prepared by a process of compressing the powders into flakes in a hydraulic press (Specac), crushing and sieving (0.3-0.5 mm).

2.2. Characterization techniques. The catalysts were characterized by wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF), BET measurements, X-ray diffraction (XRD), ultraviolet-visible diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-vis-DRS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), temperature programmed reduction with hydrogen (H₂-TPR), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and NH₃ adsorption followed by thermogravimetry (NH₃-TPD).

Wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence analysis was carried out with AXIOS PANalytical spectrometer equipped with a Rh tube. Prior to analysis the samples were prepared by the fusion method using a Spectromelt A12 flux supplied by Merck. Textural properties were evaluated from the nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms, determined at -196 °C with a Micromeritics TRISTAR II 3020 apparatus. The specific areas of the samples were determined in line with the standard BET procedure, using nitrogen adsorption taken in the relative equilibrium pressure interval of 0.03-0.3. Mean pore size was calculated using the BJH method. The samples were previously degassed overnight under nitrogen flow.

X-ray diffraction studies were conducted on a X'PERT-MPD X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and Ni filter. The X-ray tube was operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. The samples were scanned between 10° (2 θ) and 70°-80° (2 θ), and the X-ray diffraction line positions were determined with a step size of 0.026° (2 θ) and a counting time of 400 s. Phase identification was conducted by comparison with JCPDS (Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards) database cards. The oxidation states and the coordination of Ni species were evaluated by diffuse reflectance UV-vis

spectroscopy (UV-vis-DRS) with a UV-vis-NIR Cary 5000 apparatus coupled to Diffuse Reflectance Internal 2500 within a range of 350-2500 nm.

The total acidity of the catalysts was evaluated by NH_3 adsorption at 100 °C followed by thermogravimetry. These experiments were carried out with a Setaram Setsys Evolution thermobalance under atmospheric pressure coupled to a Pfeiffer Prisma mass spectrometer. Prior to adsorption experiments, the samples were first pre-treated in a helium stream at 850 °C (10 °C min^{-1}) and then cooled to 100 °C (40 °C min^{-1}). Later, the NH_3 adsorption step was performed by admitting a flow of 10% NH_3/He at 100 °C up to saturation. Subsequently, the samples were exposed to a flow of helium ($50\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$) for 90 min at 100 °C to remove reversibly and physically bound ammonia from the surface. The net weight gain was considered as the total acidity of the samples.

Redox behaviour was examined by temperature-programmed reduction and the experiments were conducted on a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument. Firstly, all the samples (30 mg) were pre-treated in an oxygen stream (5% O_2/He) at 550 °C for 1 h and then cooled to room temperature. The reducing gas used in all experiments was 5% H_2/Ar , with a flow rate of $50\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$. The temperature range explored was from room temperature to 950 °C, with a heating rate of 5 °C min^{-1} . This temperature was maintained for 1 h. The water produced by reduction was trapped in a cold trap, and the consumption of H_2 was quantitatively measured by time integration of the TPR profiles. The samples were additionally characterised by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. XPS measurements were performed with a Phoibos 150 1D-DLD analysis system from Specs, with monochromatic $\text{Al K}\alpha$ radiation (1486.6 eV). The conductivity of the samples was enhanced by the use of an electron flood gun. The samples were not sputter-cleaned before measurement. The hemispheric photoelectron analyser worked

with a pass energy of 40 eV for survey scan and 20 eV for detail scan. In order to compare all spectra recorded, the C 1s core level attributed to adventitious carbon present in the samples was used as a reference, whose binding energy was fixed at 284.6 eV. Peaks areas of Ni²⁺ including satellites were fitted with a non-linear least squares fitting program using a properly weighted sum of Lorentzian and Gaussian component curves after background subtraction according to Shirley.

The morphology and particle size distribution of the nickel particles was examined by transmission electron microscopy. Prior to analysis, the samples were dispersed in absolute ethanol ultrasonically for 30 min, and 10 cm³ of each sample were then placed on flexible film (Parafilm® M). Glow-discharged carbon-coated copper grids were inverted onto the droplets of each sample. After incubation for 1 min at room temperature, the grids were manually blotted with filter paper air-dried. Digitally recorded 2D images of each solution were taken at room temperature at a nominal magnification of 80000 on a Jeol JEM-1230 transmission electron microscope, with a LaB₆ filament as the source of electrons and operated at 100 kV. Digital images were recorded on an Orius SC1000 cooled slow-scan CCD camera, 4008×2672 pixels (GATAN), obtaining a final pixel size of 0.85 Å pixel⁻¹. The particle size distribution was obtained from the measurement of at least 300 particles using ImageJ software.

The amount of carbonaceous deposits on the used catalyst was determined by dynamic thermogravimetry using a Setaram Setsys Evolution apparatus under atmospheric pressure coupled to a Pfeiffer Prisma mass spectrometer. The mass loss and the sample temperature were continuously recorded by a computerised data acquisition system. Previously, the samples (20 mg) were dried from room temperature to 150 °C. Then, the temperature was increased from 150 to 850 °C at a constant heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹.

The oxidant stream was 5%O₂/He (50 cm³ min⁻¹) flowing downwards onto the cylindrical sample holder.

2.3. Catalyst activity determination. Catalytic tests were performed in a bench-scale fixed-bed reactor (Microactivity modular laboratory system provided by PID Eng&Tech S.L) operated at atmospheric pressure and fully monitored by computer. The reactor was made of stainless steel with an internal diameter of 9 mm and a height of 305 mm, in which the temperature was controlled with a thermocouple placed in the catalyst bed. Typically 0.125 g of catalyst in powdered form (0.3-0.5 mm) was loaded. The catalyst bed was diluted with inert quartz (0.875 g, 1-1.25 mm). A feed gas mixture containing CH₄/H₂O/N₂ = 1/3/6 was used for which a volume hourly space velocity was maintained at 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ using Bronkhorst mass flow controllers. Before the reaction, the Ni-based catalysts were reduced in situ under 5%H₂/N₂ at 850 °C for 2 h. Catalytic activity, product distribution and stability were recorded during 12.5 h at constant temperature (450 °C/550 °C/650 °C/550 °C/450 °C) with an accumulated time online of about 63 h. Feed and effluent streams were analyzed online by a MicroGC (Agilent 3000) equipped with a TCD detector. Two columns, Molecular Sieve 5A and Plot U, were used in a series/bypass arrangement for the complete separation of H₂, N₂, CH₄, CO and CO₂. A cold trap at the outlet of the reactor was used to condense out any water from the product gas stream. On basis of the molar flow at the inlet and outlet of the reactor, conversion and product yields were calculated, according to the following equations:

$$X(CH_4), \% = \frac{F(CO_{out}) + F(CO_{2,out})}{F(CH_{4,in})} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Y(H_2) = \frac{F(H_{2,out})}{2 \cdot F(CH_{4,in})} \quad (2)$$

$$Y(CO) = \frac{F(CO_{,out})}{F(CH_{4,in})} \quad (3)$$

$$Y(CO_2) = \frac{F(CO_{2,out})}{F(CH_{4,in})} \quad (4)$$

The thermodynamic data were calculated via the HSC Chemistry software package by the GIBBS program using the so-called Gibbs Energy Minimization Method.³⁰ For these calculations, only enthalpy, entropy and heat capacity data for all prevailing compounds were needed. The software calculated the amounts of products at equilibrium under isothermal and isobaric conditions. The substances to be taken into account in the calculations, the amount of reactants, the potentially stable phases as well as the temperature of raw species were specified as input. In addition to solid carbon, the following substances in the gas phase were considered: CH₄, N₂, CO, CO₂, H₂ and H₂O. Calculations were performed in the 450-650 °C temperature range at atmospheric pressure. Hence, the GIBBS program found the most stable phase combination and determined the phase composition where the Gibbs energy for the system reached its minimum at constant pressure and temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physicochemical characterization of nickel-alumina spinel catalysts. In order to rationalize the obtained catalytic results the samples were thoroughly characterized by a number of analytical techniques, namely WDXRF, BET measurements, H₂-TPR, XRD, UV-vis-DRS, XPS and TEM. The ultimate goal was to establish relationships among the structural features of the calcined catalytic precursors, the resultant catalytic properties after activation by high-temperature reduction and the performance in the studied reforming process.

The textural properties of the calcined catalysts were examined by nitrogen adsorption-desorption measurements at low temperatures. All the samples exhibited IV-type isotherms (not shown), indicating the existence of well developed mesopores with significantly reduced hysteresis loops for all the catalysts. In addition to the Ni loading determined by WDXRF, the specific surface area, pore volume and average pore size are included in Table 1. As for the bulk samples it was noted that the oxide prepared by coprecipitation exhibited significantly higher surface area and pore volume ($76 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $0.35 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$) than its D(33) counterpart ($55 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $0.14 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$). These values were consistent with those recently reported by Muroyama et al.²³ for NiAl_2O_4 spinels prepared by the citric acid complex method and calcined at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($67 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($33 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). The alumina ($\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) used for the supported catalysts, which was calcined at $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 8 h, had a surface area of $133 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. Irrespective of the synthesis route for incorporating the nickel phase the surface area of the resultant supported catalysts expectedly decreased with nickel loading ($94 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for CP/A(17) and $75\text{-}77 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for CI/A(24) and CP/A(24) samples). A simultaneous decrease in pore volume was also found, suggesting that the deposited Ni blocked some pores in the support.³¹ After the severe reduction step, which provoked the transformation of the NiAl_2O_4 -based precursors into an active $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ system, the surface area and the pore volume diminished by about 10-30% (Table 1). Hence, the reduced CP/A(17) catalyst showed the highest surface area ($84 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$).

Table 1

The analysis of the synthesized catalytic precursors by H_2 -TPR was performed in order to identify the nickel species present in each sample, their relative abundance and reducibility (Figure 1). For comparative purposes the profile of a pure NiO sample, obtained by simple calcination of nickel acetate at $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h in air, was also

included. It was noted that the H₂ uptake was noticeable in a wide temperature range and the reduction process was complete at 950 °C. Although not shown in Figure 1, no reduction peaks were observed on the bare alumina support. In general, the profiles showed two main reduction bands located between 200-600 °C and 600-950 °C. The band at lower temperatures was much more visible for the D(33) and CI/A(24) samples while its contribution to the overall hydrogen consumption resulted less significant for the samples prepared by coprecipitation (CP samples). Table 2 includes the overall H₂ uptake of the catalysts determined both experimentally and theoretically. Since a fairly good agreement was found between both values for all the samples it was then concluded that the reduction process was complete.

Figure 1/Table 2

Typically the reducible Ni²⁺ species are divided into three types: α , β and γ .³²⁻³⁴ The γ -type species (with a reduction temperature higher than 800 °C) corresponded to the NiAl₂O₄ spinel while the α -type species (with a reduction temperature at 350-530 °C) were related to easily reducible, free NiO. The nickel species with reducibility at moderate temperatures (600-760 °C) were identified as β -type species assignable to Ni²⁺ ions that were not completely integrated into the spinel. In this sense, Zhang et al.³⁵ suggested that these Ni²⁺ ions are NiO in a Ni-rich mixed oxide phase (more reducible β_1 species) or NiO in a Al-rich mixed oxide phase (less reducible β_2 species). A Gaussian-type deconvolution was applied to characterize the types of reducible nickel species in terms of relative abundance and reduction temperatures (Table 2).

As for the bulk oxides it was clear that the sample prepared by coprecipitation (CP(33)) contained a notably lower amount of free NiO species (lower than 10%) with respect to the D(33) sample (about 33%). In the CP(33) sample the Ni²⁺ species were almost equally distributed between β - and γ -type species (47 and 44%, respectively). An

additional difference in reducibility of these two bulk oxides was the nature of β -type species. It was tentatively established that the coprecipitated sample essentially contained β_2 species with a relatively similar structure (defect/non-stoichiometric nickel aluminate phase) to the pure spinel phase. The reduction temperature was 760 °C. In contrast, the D(33) sample mainly contained β_1 species that were reduced at considerably lower temperatures (625 °C).

Three deconvoluted reduction bands were also noticed for the two alumina supported samples prepared by coprecipitation. These were located at 445-480 °C (α -type), 645-665 °C (β -type) and 800 °C (γ -type). When compared with the CP(33) bulk sample, the reduction process occurred at significantly lower temperatures (around 30-150 °C), thereby suggesting a favored reducibility of the supported oxides. The relative amount of γ -type species was also noticeably larger (about 75% compared with 44% for the bulk sample) while the contribution of α -type species was very similar (6-7% compared with 9% for the bulk sample). In view of the reduction temperatures of β -type species (645-665 °C) these supported coprecipitated samples mostly contained β_1 species.

Substantial differences were found in the deconvoluted H_2 -TPR profiles of the CI/A(24) and CP/A(24) oxides. While having the same Ni content it was evident that the used synthesis route considerably influenced the distribution of Ni^{2+} species. Thus, coprecipitation favored the massive formation of γ -type ($NiAl_2O_4$) species (74% for the coprecipitated sample in contrast to 52% for the coimpregnated sample) and minimized the amount of free α -NiO (7% for the coprecipitated sample in contrast to 28% for the coimpregnated sample). These features were also observed for the bulk CP(33) coprecipitated sample. It could be then concluded that the chemical nature of the Ni^{2+} species present on the D(33) and CI/A(24) samples was significantly more heterogeneous with respect to their counterparts prepared by coprecipitation. Therefore,

the routes based on dissolution followed by crystallization and wet coimpregnation were not efficient for producing NiAl_2O_4 -rich catalytic precursors with a reduced presence of free NiO.

The structural features of the calcined catalysts were also analyzed by means of XRD and UV-vis-DRS. The corresponding XRD patterns are included in Figure 2. The obtained crystalline phases were identified using the JCPDS files. The diffractogram of the alumina support calcined at 850 °C (JCPDS 79-1558) was included for comparison. All the bulk and alumina supported catalytic prepared samples showed a set of diffractions peaks at $2\theta = 19.3^\circ$, 31.5° , 37.2° , 45.2° , 59.9° and 65.7° , assignable to a nickel aluminate phase.^{6,19} Although H_2 -TPR analysis evidenced the notable presence of NiO in the D(33) and CI/A(24) samples, this was only confirmed by XRD for the D(33) catalyst with the signals at $2\theta = 43.5^\circ$ and 62.9° (JCPDS 89-7131) (with an average crystallite size of about 30 nm). The absence of NiO signals in the pattern of CI/A(24) samples could be explained by the fact that the crystallites were smaller than their detection limit (2-5 nm).⁶ On the other hand, in addition to the signals corresponding to NiAl_2O_4 , the patterns of the alumina-supported expectedly should contain the signals attributable to the support. However, since the most intense signals of the alumina are close to those of the spinel phase, the clearest evidence of the presence of the support was perhaps given by the shoulder peak at $2\theta = 67.0^\circ$. The formation of NiAl_2O_4 and mixtures of NiO/ NiAl_2O_4 could be also qualitatively assessed by the color of the calcined catalytic precursors. While all the CP samples and the CI/A(24) sample were dark blue, an indication of the substantial presence of NiAl_2O_4 , the D(33) sample was greenish-blue (an evidence of the presence of green NiO).

Figure 2

Finally the coordination of the nickel species present in the different samples was examined by UV-vis-DRS. This technique was helpful in providing additional evidences for the identification of the nickel phases. Figure 3 shows the UV-vis-DRS spectra of the investigated catalytic precursors. The bands located at 380, 420 (absent on the CP samples) and 720 nm represent the octahedrally coordinated Ni^{2+} species in NiO lattices, while those at 550 nm and in the range of 600-650 nm were related to the tetrahedrally coordinated Ni^{2+} species in the nickel aluminate lattice.^{5,36,37} Based on the fact that the characteristic bands of nickel aluminate were more intense in all the samples, the predominant presence of the spinel was further confirmed.

Figure 3

XPS analysis of the calcined precursors offered valuable information regarding with the surface composition and the oxidation state of nickel species. For each sample two photoemission peaks were shown: Ni $2p_{3/2}$ (875-845 eV) and O 1s (540-520 eV) (Figure 4 (A) and (B), respectively). For peak identification the spectra were previously deconvoluted on the basis of the constraints of equal spin-orbit splitting for Ni 2p peaks and the area ratio of Ni $2p_{3/2}$ and Ni $2p_{1/2}$ being constant at approximately 2 (theoretical value).³⁸ In Figure 4 (A) two main bands were observed for all the calcined samples. Hence, the band located at 855.6 eV corresponded to the Ni $2p_{3/2}$ peak and the band at 861.6 eV corresponded to the typical shake-up satellite peak. While the signal at 855.6 eV exhibited a good symmetry in the samples prepared by coprecipitation (CP(33), CP/A(24) and CP/A(17)), thereby indicating the presence of one single type of Ni^{2+} species, this was not the case for the D(33) and CI/A(24) samples. Thus, the band was markedly wider and not well resolved. In an attempt to distinguish the nature of the oxidized metal these spectra were deconvoluted into two components (856.8 and 854.1 eV). This suggested that Ni was apparently distributed between two sites

(Figure 4 (A)). The band at 854.1 eV was associated with NiO whereas the band at 856.8 eV was attributed to Ni²⁺ ions in the network of NiAl₂O₄ spinel phase.³⁹ The relative contributions of the deconvoluted peaks corresponding to NiAl₂O₄ and NiO phases are summarized in Table 2. It was thus found that a significant amount of nickel was present as NiO (62% for the D(33) sample and 45% for the CI/A(24) sample). Contrastingly this phase was not detected in the coprecipitated samples. Moreover, the Ni/Al ratios independently evaluated from WDXRF and XPS analysis were quite similar for the CP samples while an enrichment of surface nickel was evident for the D(33) and CI/A(24) samples due to the presence of NiO species. The analysis of the O 1s spectra of the calcined precursors further corroborated the surface heterogeneity of the D(33) and CI/A(24) samples (Figure 4 (B)). Thus, the wide signal at 531 eV could be decomposed into three bands centered at 528.6, 531.2 and 532.4 eV which were associated with oxygen species in NiO, NiAl₂O₄ and Al₂O₃, respectively.^{39,40} On the contrary, the O 1s band located at 531 eV showed a relatively good symmetry for the CP samples. This feature was reasonably related to the predominant presence of nickel aluminate on the surface. In sum, the simultaneous presence of NiO+NiAl₂O₄ in the D(33) and CI/A(24) samples and the predominant presence of NiAl₂O₄ in the coprecipitated samples was confirmed at the surface level, in line with the previous bulk characterization.

Figure 4

The reduced samples (submitted to a reduction step at 850 °C for 2 h with 5% H₂/N₂) were analyzed by XRD and TEM. This was the activation procedure used in situ in the reactor prior to steam reforming runs. The XRD patterns are shown in Figure 2 ((b) samples). It was found that Ni²⁺ species (as NiAl₂O₄ in CP samples and a NiO/NiAl₂O₄ mixture in the D(33) and CI/A(24) samples) were massively reduced into

metallic Ni (JCPDS 89-7128, peaks at $2\theta = 44.6^\circ$, 52.0° and 76.5°). The reduction of the spinel phase simultaneously involved the formation of the alumina phase. Although this process was expected for all the calcined precursors, it could be more easily observed for the bulk samples since they did not contain alumina as a support in the original catalyst formulation.

Figure 5 include the TEM micrographs and particle size distribution diagrams, which were obtained from the measurement of the size of more than 300 particles, of the nickel-alumina spinel catalysts. These graphs are expressed in terms of both frequency and accumulated frequency as a function of metallic particle size. When comparing the results obtained for the bulk samples (D(33) and CP(33)) clear differences were observed. Thus, while the distribution was relatively symmetrical for the CP(33) catalyst (5-20 nm) a much higher heterogeneity was noticed for the D(33) sample (within the range 5-30 nm). This sample contained a significant fraction (>20%) of particles with a size larger than 20 nm. In contrast, all the measured sizes of the particles (99%) in the CP(33) catalyst were lower than 20 nm. The average size estimated for an accumulated frequency of 95% was 15.8 and 10.1 nm for D(33) and CP(33), respectively. It is believed that the reduction of NiO present in the D(33) sample resulted in larger Ni sizes while the CP(33) sample, with a more homogeneous surface composition, led to significantly smaller particles.

Figure 5

The analysis of the histograms of the CI/A(24) and D(33) samples prepared following a similar synthesis route pointed out the advantages of the introduction of alumina as a support in the catalyst formulation. Hence, the average size decreased from 15.8 (D(33) sample) to 10.2 nm (CI/A(24) sample). Although the CI/A(24) sample also contained a significant quantity of nickel species as free α -NiO its low size did not probably induce

the formation of large Ni particles. The same conclusions could be derived from the comparison of CP(33) and CP/A(24) samples although the differences in average Ni particles size were less marked (9.5 nm for CP/A(24) and 10.1 nm for CP(33)). This was related to the fact that the presence of α -type species was similar in both cases. On the other hand, when evaluating the influence of the preparation method of alumina supported catalysts with the same Ni loading (CI/A(24) and CP/A(24)), a slightly lower size (9.5 nm) was noted for CP/A(24) with respect to CI/A(24) (10.2 nm). A closer inspection of the particle size distribution revealed 65 and 92% of the particles of CP/A(24) were smaller than 10 and 15 nm, respectively. The corresponding values for CI/A(24) were 57 and 87%. Finally, it must be pointed out that a virtually identical average particle size (9.5 nm) was obtained for CP/A(24) and CP/A(17) samples. This was somewhat lower than that obtained for the bulk counterpart (CP(33), 10.1 nm). From the average particle size of each sample the corresponding values for nickel dispersion and nickel surface area were determined (Table 3). It was observed that the highest values were obtained for the coprecipitated samples. Thus, the CP/A(17) catalyst showed a dispersion of 33% and a metallic surface area of about $40 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. Also noteworthy were the relatively high values (9.5% and $23 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively) for the CP(33) sample in spite of being a bulk catalyst.

Table 3

An attempt to evaluate the Ni crystallite size was also made by XRD. Because the overlap between Al_2O_3 (400) ($2\theta = 45.7^\circ$) diffraction line and the most intensive metallic Ni (111) ($2\theta = 44.6^\circ$), Ni (200) ($2\theta = 52.0^\circ$) diffraction line was used to calculate the metallic Ni crystallite size with Scherrer equation. The FWHM was obtained with WINPLOTR software. The results are given in Table 3. A very good agreement between the results given by TEM and XRD was found for the CP samples.

This indicated that no crystallite agglomeration occurred in these samples. Nevertheless, a certain divergence was noted for the CI/A(24) and D(33) samples although the same trend was valid since the size of D(33) was again larger than that of CI/A(24). This growth observed by XRD concerned various crystallographic planes which did not affect the peak diffraction positions. Giallonardo et al.⁴¹ showed that the growth faults may be due to stacking faults which are not caused by deformation processes. Moreover, it is believed that these stacking faults could be related to the heterogeneity concluded from the TEM particle size distribution and H₂-TPR profiles for D and CI samples.

In view of both TEM and XRD results it could be concluded that the massive presence of nickel as NiAl₂O₄, which was successfully attained by the coprecipitation route, instead of mixtures NiO+NiAl₂O₄ was important for obtaining small Ni particles. Furthermore, the introduction of alumina as a support in the catalyst formulation slightly decreased the Ni average size.

3.2. Catalytic behavior of nickel-alumina spinel catalysts in steam reforming of methane. The catalytic performance was examined by recording, on a dry basis, methane conversion (equation 1) and yields of H₂ (equation 2), CO (equation 3) and CO₂ (equation 4) during 12.5 hours at constant temperature (450 °C/550 °C/650 °C/550 °C/450 °C) with an accumulated time online of about 63 h. As aforementioned, the catalysts were in situ activated by reduction with a flow of 5%H₂/N₂ at 850 °C for 2 h. It was previously confirmed by H₂-TPR that under these conditions the samples were completely reduced.

The proposed five-run test was useful for analyzing the catalytic behavior at a given reaction temperature during a reasonable time on stream (12.5 h) and gaining insight

into the catalytic stability when decreasing the reaction temperature from a higher (650 °C) to a lower value (550 and 450 °C) during the same time interval (12.5 h). The test was carried out at a constant volume hourly space velocity of $38400 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ with a feed stream containing 10%CH₄ in excess of water with a H₂O/C ratio of 3. Previous studies on the effect of H₂O/CH₄ ratio on steam reforming of methane pointed out the need of using an excess of water in order to prevent a rapid deactivation and achieve a high hydrogen yield.^{42,43} On the other hand, it must be pointed out that calcined nickel-alumina spinel catalysts exhibited a poor activity.

The catalytic results in terms of the evolution of the yield of H₂ as a function of temperature and time on line are shown in Figure 6. Additionally Table 4 includes the time-averaged (for a reaction time interval of 12.5 h) values for conversion and yields of reforming products at the examined temperatures. Expectedly, conversion increased with temperature, from 4-21% at 450 °C to 53-80% at 650 °C. Simultaneously notable yields of H₂, CO and CO₂ were detected. Table 4 also lists the values for H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios. It could be observed that at low temperatures (450 °C) the yield of CO was almost negligible while the yield of CO₂ was relatively significant. This was simultaneously accompanied by very high H₂/CO ratios (68-119). This product distribution clearly indicated that the contribution of the water gas shift reaction ($\text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \leftrightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2$) was considerably relevant. On increasing the reaction temperature the H₂/CO ratio notably decreased to values ranging from 6.9 to 8.7 at 650 °C. Concurrently, the CO/CO₂ ratio increased but less markedly (up to 1.0 to 1.4). These observations pointed out that at high temperatures, where the yield of hydrogen was high, the reverse water gas shift reaction ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \leftrightarrow \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$) was noticeably activated. On the other hand, it could be noted that the concentrations at the exit gas

were stable with time on stream for each selected reaction temperature and consequently there was no appreciable catalyst deactivation.

Figure 6/Table 4

Irrespective of the reaction temperature the CP(33), CP/A(17) and CP/A(24) samples were clearly the most active catalysts. In fact, these catalysts showed a comparable performance at high temperatures (650 °C), with a small difference in conversion (75-80%) and a similar yield of H₂. Hence, the following trend for methane conversion and H₂ yield could be noticed: CP(33) > CP/A(17) > CP/A(24) > CI/A(24) > D(33). This trend was further corroborated at lower temperatures (450 and 550 °C). The highest yield of H₂ (1.63) was attained by the bulk nickel aluminate prepared by coprecipitation (CP(33)) followed by the CP/A(17) sample (1.59). This yield was related to a conversion of methane into CO and CO₂ of around 80% (the corresponding equilibrium conversion was 97%). In view of these results it was clear that the nickel loading could be considerably decreased from 33 to 17 wt.% by using the coprecipitation route on a ceramic support such as alumina.

In order to rationalize these results and particularly to gain insight into the relationship between the structural features of the nickel catalysts and the observed performance in the reaction, the corresponding rate constants normalized by the amount of accessible nickel, in terms of metallic surface area, were estimated. Hence a rate expression that assumed the rate was only a function of methane partial pressure was considered.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ The normalized rate constants were calculated at the three investigated temperatures (Table 5). When analyzing independently the behavior of the three supported samples (CI/A(24), CP/A(24) and CP/A(17)) it was found that the rate constants were relatively similar for CP/A samples and these were appreciably higher than that corresponding to the CI/A(24) sample. Since the metallic surface area of these

coprecipitated samples was also significantly larger, higher conversion levels were consequently noticed in comparison with the CI/A(24) sample, as shown in Figure 7. On the other hand, it seemed that a further increase in metallic surface area from 34 to 40 m² g⁻¹ did not result in a marked promotion of activity.

It was evident that the coprecipitation route led to structurally homogeneous NiAl₂O₄ catalysts (supported CP samples) with a relatively reduced presence of NiO species. After high-temperature reduction which resulted in the formation of small nickel crystallites (9.5 nm), a relatively high dispersion and a large metallic surface area were achieved. In contrast, the CI/A(24) sample with a slightly larger crystallite size (10.2 nm), assigned to the significant abundance of NiO species in the calcined catalytic precursor, exhibited a smaller metallic surface area (31 m² g⁻¹) and, in turn, a markedly poorer activity. Activity of these alumina-supported samples seemed to be also controlled by an increased pore volume. However, the pore size of the samples was considered to be large enough to play a relevant role on catalytic performance.

On the other hand, as for the bulk catalysts (D(33) and CP(33) samples) both samples exhibited a quite similar normalized rate constant irrespective of the reaction temperature. This indicated that the intrinsic activity of the nickel sites was the same. Nevertheless, the coprecipitation route was more efficient for increasing the available metallic surface area as crystallites with a lower size were formed after high-temperature reduction. Consequently, conversion was substantially higher (80% compared with 53% at 650 °C). This in turn was related to the absence of NiO in the calcined precursor. Note that the pore volume of the coprecipitated sample was markedly larger as well.

Table 5/Figure 7

Figures 6 and 7 evidenced that the samples that gave the highest conversion (> 550 °C) were coprecipitated CP(33) and CP/A(17) catalysts. In fact, both displayed a comparable reforming efficiency. As shown in Table 5 the normalized rate constant of the bulk sample was twice that of CP/A(17) sample. It is speculated that the intrinsic activity of nickel crystallites, closely related to the nature of the metal-support interaction and the characteristics of the support, is not the same. Note that the alumina support created by the high-temperature reduction of the bulk sample was different from that of the commercial alumina support used for the synthesis of the CP/A(17) sample. This was mainly reflected by the different surface area and mean pore size (Table 1) as well as the acidity ($240 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for the CP(33) sample and $302 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for the CP/A(17) sample) of these two reduced catalysts, which was estimated from NH_3 adsorption followed by thermogravimetry. In principle, a lower overall acidity is expected to inhibit the formation of coke precursors that might have a negative impact on conversion. This could be the reason for the higher intrinsic activity of the CP(33) catalyst.

Furthermore, a preliminary analysis of these two spent catalysts by XRD (patterns not shown) revealed that both catalysts retained metallic nickel. An estimation of the size of the Ni particles by the Scherrer equation from the Ni (200) diffraction line was made. Hence, the nickel crystallite size of the used bulk coprecipitated catalyst was 11 nm, virtually identical to the fresh counterpart. Moreover, the surface area of the spent catalyst was $52 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (very similar to $55 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ of the freshly reduced counterpart). Contrastingly, a significant increase in the size from 9 nm to 13 nm was evident for the CP/A(17) sample, which was accompanied by a slight decrease in the surface area (from 84 to $74 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). This indicated that the thermal stability of Ni crystallites was lower for the supported catalyst under the studied reforming conditions. However, in view of its

stable performance with time at varying temperatures, it was suggested that this sintering occurred very fast and did not have a dramatic impact on activity. Also the eventual formation of coke was investigated by temperature programmed oxidation followed by coupled to mass spectrometry. Since the evolution of the CO₂ (m/z = 44) signal was almost flat, the presence of carbonaceous deposits was negligible in both samples.

On the other hand, in addition to exhibiting a similar conversion efficiency and a remarkable stability both CP(33) and CP/A(17) samples gave comparable H₂/CO (6.9-7.3 at 650 °C) and CO/CO₂ (1.3-1.4 at 650 °C) ratios. This corresponded to a value of CO concentration (on a dry basis) of 4.2-4.5%.

Anyway, on the basis of the need to minimize the cost associated with the metallic phase and its notable activity and stability, the CP/A(17) sample was considered the most suitable among the investigated nickel catalysts for methane steam reforming at low temperatures. In this sense an attempt was made to compare the behavior of this optimum catalyst in relation with the main studies devoted to the methane steam reforming at low temperatures over Ni-based catalysts (Table 6). As can be seen a wide variety of supports have been examined including Al₂O₃, CeO₂, CeO₂-ZrO₂, La₂O₃, MgO and MgAl₂O₄.^{9,14,47-51} Generally the metal loading is in the 5-20 wt.% Ni range while the reforming temperature is typically between 500 and 650 °C. On the other hand, the investigated volume hourly space velocity is between 2000 and 40000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹. In our case attention was mainly focused on the catalytic results obtained at space velocities higher than 10000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ since this is in the range of our VHSV (38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹). Thus, Zhou et al.¹⁴ achieved 90% conversion at 39250 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹ and 650 °C over 18 wt.% Ni/NiAl₂O₄/γ-Al₂O₃/alloy. At this same temperature but at a considerably lower VHSV (18000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹) Kim et al.⁹

reported a good reforming activity over 10 wt.% Ni/MgAl₂O₄ (91%) and 10 wt.% Ni/Al₂O₃ (87%). Similarly, de Freitas Silva et al.⁴⁷ reached 65% conversion over 18 wt.% Ni/Al₂O₃ at 16000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹. The catalytic activity was noticeably promoted when adding CeO₂ (4.5 wt.% Ce) and La₂O₃ (3.2 wt.% La) as promoters with a 91% conversion at the same experimental conditions.

Table 6

CeO₂-ZrO₂-based catalysts also exhibited a remarkable reforming performance with conversion values around 60% at 600 °C and 36570 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹.⁴⁸ This activity was comparable to that obtained by our CP/A(17) sample at a slightly higher VHSV (with an estimated conversion value of 62% at 600 °C). Likewise, Parizotto et al.⁴⁹ evaluated a 15 wt.% Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst at high VHSV (42000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹). Conversion was relatively poor (30%) probably due to the low H₂O/CH₄ ratio (0.5) used. This behavior was in line with the results obtained by Yamazaki et al.⁵⁰ over Ni_{0.03}Mg_{0.97}O (4.3 wt.% Ni) at a H₂O/CH₄ ratio of 1 (43% conversion at 10000 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹). A similar conversion value (40%) was found by Hoang et al.⁵¹ using a NiS(10 wt.% Ni)/Al₂O₃ catalyst at 22400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹. In sum, on the basis of these results reported in the literature it can be considered that coprecipitated NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ are promising nickel catalysts for the low-temperature steam reforming operating at high VHSV.

4. Conclusions

Results obtained for performance of the investigated NiAl₂O₄ spinel-based systems in the steam reforming of methane at low temperatures operated at relatively high volume hourly space velocity revealed the superiority of the samples prepared by

coprecipitation in producing catalysts with better structural features. This was valid for both bulk and alumina supported catalysts.

The activity was mainly controlled by the structural homogeneity of the Ni²⁺ species present in the catalyst (NiAl₂O₄ instead of NiO). This had an important impact on the size of the Ni crystallites, dispersion and metallic surface area after reduction. The presence of NiO species, which was significant (25-27%) for the samples obtained by dissolution followed by crystallization and coimpregnation, was not desirable since its reduction led to catalysts with worse properties (larger particle sizes and lower dispersion and metallic surface) with a poorer reforming efficiency. Thus, the synthesis route based on coprecipitation was suitable for preparing highly active catalysts mainly consisting of NiAl₂O₄ phase.

Taking into consideration the exhibited activity and stability and the nickel loading the most promising sample was the coprecipitated alumina-supported (17 wt.%Ni)NiAl₂O₄ catalyst. The main changes noticed for this catalyst after reaction was a slight sintering and loss of surface area. However, the extent of these deactivating phenomena was not large since the stability was high during a time on stream of about 60 h. Also noteworthy was the remarkable performance of the bulk coprecipitated spinel catalyst. This sample was characterized by a moderate dispersion and nickel surface area in comparison with the supported samples although it showed a high specific activity and a notable thermal and chemical stability. Finally it should be noticed that the nickel catalysts derived from coprecipitated NiAl₂O₄ precursor can be considered very interesting systems in comparison with those reported in the literature.

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Table 1. Composition and textural properties of the nickel-alumina spinel catalysts.

Catalyst	Ni, wt.%*	Ni/Al atomic ratio*	S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹	d _p , Å
γ-Al ₂ O ₃	---	---	133	0.55	124
D(33)	33	0.5	55 (48)	0.14 (0.12)	75 (81)
CP(33)	33	0.5	76 (55)	0.35 (0.32)	154 (192)
CI/A(24)	24	0.3	75 (62)	0.27 (0.24)	113 (122)
CP/A(24)	24	0.3	77 (57)	0.40 (0.31)	158 (170)
CP/A(17)	17	0.2	94 (84)	0.46 (0.34)	142 (132)

*Determined by WDXRF.

Values in brackets correspond to the textural properties of the reduced catalysts.

Table 2. H₂ uptake (as determined by H₂-TPR), relative abundance of Ni²⁺ species (as determined by H₂-TPR and XPS) and surface Ni/Al ratio (XPS) of the calcined nickel-alumina spinel catalysts.

Catalyst	Theoretical H ₂ uptake, mmol H ₂ g ⁻¹	Experimental H ₂ uptake, mmol H ₂ g ⁻¹	Relative amount of NiO species*, %			Ni/Al**	Ni ²⁺ as NiO**, %	Ni ²⁺ as NiAl ₂ O ₄ **, %
			α	β	γ			
D(33)	5.6	5.8±0.1	33 (400)	18 (625)	49 (795)	1	62	38
CP(33)	5.6	5.6±0.1	9 (530)	47 (760)	44 (830)	0.6	0	100
CI/A(24)	4.1	4.0±0.1	28 (370)	20 (725)	52 (825)	0.8	46	54
CP/A(24)	4.1	4.2±0.1	7 (480)	19 (665)	74 (800)	0.3	0	100
CP/A(17)	2.9	2.8±0.1	6 (445)	19 (645)	75 (795)	0.2	0	100

*Determined by H₂-TPR analysis. Values in parentheses correspond to the peak temperature (°C) of each reduction band.

**Determined by XPS.

Table 2

Table 3. Nickel crystallite size (as determined by TEM and XRD), nickel dispersion and nickel surface area (as determined by TEM) of the reduced nickel-alumina spinel catalysts.

Catalyst	Ni crystallite size, nm	Ni dispersion, %	Ni surface area, m ² g ⁻¹
D(33)	15.8 (23)	4	10
CP(33)	10.1 (11)	9.5	23
CI/A(24)	10.2 (13)	18	31
CP/A(24)	9.5 (9)	20	34
CP/A(17)	9.5 (9)	33	40

Values in brackets correspond to the Ni crystallite size obtained by XRD analysis from Ni (200).

Table 4. Catalytic performance of the reduced nickel-alumina spinel catalysts in terms of time-averaged (12.5 h) CH₄ conversion, yields of H₂, CO and CO₂ and H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios at different temperatures.

Catalyst	X(CH ₄), %			Y(H ₂)			Y(CO)			Y(CO ₂)			H ₂ /CO			CO/CO ₂		
	450	550	650	450	550	650	450	550	650	450	550	650	450	550	650	450	550	650
Equilibrium	40	74	97	0.8	1.4	1.68	0.04	0.23	0.51	0.37	0.51	0.46	45	12	6.7	0.1	0.4	1.1
D(33)	9	29	53	0.2	0.7	1.14	4·10 ⁻³	0.07	0.27	0.08	0.22	0.26	119	19	8.5	4.7·10 ⁻²	0.3	1.0
CP(33)	21	52	80	0.5	1.2	1.63	0.01	0.18	0.47	0.19	0.35	0.33	68	13	6.9	0.1	0.5	1.4
CI/A(24)	4	26	61	0.1	0.7	1.32	0.0	0.05	0.30	0.04	0.21	0.31	-	27	8.7	0.0	0.2	1.0
CP/A(24)	17	46	75	0.4	1.1	1.57	0.01	0.14	0.42	0.16	0.33	0.34	80	16	7.5	0.1	0.4	1.2
CP/A(17)	14	47	78	0.4	1.1	1.59	0.01	0.13	0.44	0.13	0.33	0.34	86	16	7.3	0.1	0.4	1.3

Reaction conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/N₂; W = 0.125 g.

Table 5. Normalised rate constant (k) for the various investigated catalysts at different temperatures.

Catalyst	$k(\times 10^3), \text{ mol s}^{-1} \text{ m}_{\text{Ni}}^{-2} \text{ MPa}_{\text{CH}_4}^{-1}$			$k, \text{ mol s}^{-1} \text{ g}_{\text{Ni sup.}}^{-1} \text{ MPa}_{\text{CH}_4}^{-1}$		
	450 °C	550 °C	650 °C	450 °C	550 °C	650 °C
D(33)	4.6	16.8	37.1	3.1	11.2	24.7
CP(33)	4.9	15.2	33.3	3.2	10.1	22.2
CI/A(24)	0.6	4.6	14.5	0.4	3.1	9.7
CP/A(24)	2.6	8.5	19.2	1.7	5.7	12.8
CP/A(17)	1.8	7.5	17.9	1.2	5.0	11.9

A rate expression that assumed the rate was only a function of methane partial pressure was considered.

Table 6. Overview of the main studies on low-temperature steam reforming of methane over nickel catalysts operated at VHSV higher than $10000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$.

Catalyst	%wt. Ni	H ₂ O/CH ₄	T, °C	VHSV, cm ³ CH ₄ g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹	Conversion, %	Ref.
NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃	17	3	650	38400	78	This work
NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃	17	3	600	38400	62 ^a	This work
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	18	4	650	16000	65	(47)
Ni/CeO ₂ /La ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃	17	4	650	16000	91	(47)
Ni/MgAl ₂ O ₄	10	2	650	18000	91	(9)
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	10	2	650	18000	87	(9)
Ni/CeO ₂	10	2	650	18000	77	(9)
Ni/NiAl ₂ O ₄ /γ-Al ₂ O ₃ /alloy	18	3	650	39250	90	(14)
Ni _{0.03} Mg _{0.97} O	4.3	1	600	10000	43	(50)
NiS/Al ₂ O ₃	10	3	600	22400	40	(51)
Ni/CeO ₂	15	1	600	36570 ^c	58	(48)
Ni/CeO ₂ -ZrO ₂	15	1	600	36570 ^c	60	(48)
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	15	0.5 ^b	600	42000	30	(49)

^aEstimated conversion value from the linear relationship between conversion and temperature in the 450-650 °C range.

^bHydrogen is fed with a CH₄/H₂ ratio of 1/0.5.

^cThe volume hourly space velocity was estimated for an apparent density of 0.85 cm³ g⁻¹ for CeO₂-based catalysts.

Figure 1. H₂-TPR profiles of the calcined nickel-alumina spinel catalysts.

Figure 2. XRD patterns of the (a) calcined and (b) reduced nickel-alumina spinel catalysts.

Figure 3. UV-vis-DRS spectra of the calcined nickel-alumina spinel catalysts: (a)

CP/A(17), (b) CP/A(24), (c) CI/A(24), (d) CP(33), (e) D(33), (f) NiO.

Figure 4. XPS spectra of Ni 2p_{3/2} region (A) and O 1s region (B) of the calcined nickel-alumina spinel catalysts.

Figure 5. TEM micrographs and Ni particle size distribution of the reduced nickel-alumina spinel catalysts.

Figure 6. Catalytic performance of the reduced nickel-alumina spinel catalysts in terms of H_2 , CO and CO_2 yield at different temperatures. Reaction conditions:

$38400 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; $W = 0.125 \text{ g}$; $10\% \text{CH}_4/30\% \text{H}_2\text{O}/60\% \text{N}_2$.

Figure 7. Relationship of conversion at constant temperature (450, 550 and 650 °C) with metallic surface area of the reduced nickel-alumina spinel catalysts. Reaction conditions: $38400 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; $W = 0.125 \text{ g}$; $10\% \text{CH}_4/30\% \text{H}_2\text{O}/60\% \text{N}_2$.

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